

Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 6 to 14

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The work is also available at author's site:

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19319>

Abstract

*This work bring different ways of representing prime magic squares. These are of type: **blocks, block-bordered, concentric, nested**, etc. This work is for the orders 6 to 14 with prime number entries. Further orders from 15 to 23 are given in the next part [10]. There are magic squares such as of orders 7, 10, 11, 13, 14, etc. These are either prime number orders or double-prime number orders. There is difficulty in representing them in equal sums blocks. In case of orders 10, 14, etc. we are able bring blocks of equal prime numbers of orders 5, 7 etc. In case of 11, 13, etc. a little different approach is applied. For these types of magic squares, an external borders are considered, the internal part is represented in terms of blocks, for example, in case of order 11, 13, etc, blocks of order 9 are applied in the inner part.*

Keywords: magic squares, prime magic squares, block-wise magic squares, concentric magic squares, recreational mathematics.

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Contents

1 Introduction	3
1.1 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 8	3
1.2 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 9	3
2 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 10	4
2.1 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 11	5
2.2 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 12	5
3 Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares of Order 6-14	7
3.1 Prime Magic Squares of Order 6	8
3.2 Prime Magic Squares of Order 7	10
3.3 Prime Magic Squares of Order 8	11
3.4 Prime Magic Squares of Order 9	13
3.5 Prime Magic Squares of Order 10	17
3.6 Prime Magic Squares of Order 11	19
3.7 Prime Magic Squares of Order 12	21
3.8 Prime Magic Squares of Order 13	27
3.9 Prime Magic Squares of Order 14	29
4 Author's Contribution to Recreation of Numbers and Magic Squares	36

1 Introduction

During past years, the author studied block-wise constructions of magic squares. The work for the magic square of orders 8 to 47. Below are few examples:

1.1 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 8

Let's consider a **pandiagonal** of order 8 is given by

8x8	pan	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260
260	7	60	1	62	15	52	9	54	260
260	2	61	8	59	10	53	16	51	260
260	64	3	58	5	56	11	50	13	260
260	57	6	63	4	49	14	55	12	260
260	23	44	17	46	31	36	25	38	260
260	18	45	24	43	26	37	32	35	260
260	48	19	42	21	40	27	34	29	260
260	41	22	47	20	33	30	39	28	260
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

It is composed four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.

1.2 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 9

Let's consider a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 is given by

9x9	pan	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369
369	22	71	30	27	64	32	20	69	34
369	35	21	67	28	23	72	33	25	65
369	66	31	26	68	36	19	70	29	24
369	40	8	75	45	1	77	38	6	79
369	80	39	4	73	41	9	78	43	2
369	3	76	44	5	81	37	7	74	42
369	58	53	12	63	46	14	56	51	16
369	17	57	49	10	59	54	15	61	47
	48	13	62	50	18	55	52	11	60
	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

In this case, blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** (sum of only rows and columns) with equal magic sums.

Below is another example where blocks of order 3 are magic squares, but the magic square of order 9 is not **pandiagonal**:

9 mgc										369
31	36	29	76	81	74	13	18	11	369	
30	32	34	75	77	79	12	14	16	369	
35	28	33	80	73	78	17	10	15	369	
22	27	20	40	45	38	58	63	56	369	
21	23	25	39	41	43	57	59	61	369	
26	19	24	44	37	42	62	55	60	369	
67	72	65	4	9	2	49	54	47	369	
66	68	70	3	5	7	48	50	52	369	
71	64	69	8	1	6	53	46	51	369	
369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	

In this case, blocks of order 3 are magic squares with different magic sums.

2 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 10

Let's consider a magic square of order 10 with inner part as magic square of order 8 with blocks of order 4 is given by

10x10 mgc										505
91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92	505
13	47	58	19	78	39	66	27	70	88	505
89	22	75	50	55	30	67	42	63	12	505
11	82	23	54	43	74	31	62	35	90	505
96	51	46	79	26	59	38	71	34	5	505
1	48	57	20	77	40	65	28	69	100	505
93	21	76	49	56	29	68	41	64	8	505
7	81	24	53	44	73	32	61	36	94	505
95	52	45	80	25	60	37	72	33	6	505
9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

The blocks of order 8 are equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 10.

2.1 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 11

The **block-bordered** magic square of order 11 with inner part as magic square of order 9 is given by

11x11	mgc											671
	12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	671
	121	21	38	43	55	60	68	80	85	99	1	671
	119	53	58	72	75	92	97	28	33	41	3	671
	117	82	87	95	26	31	45	48	65	70	5	671
	115	47	25	30	69	50	64	94	81	89	7	671
	11	67	54	62	101	79	84	42	23	37	111	671
	13	96	77	91	40	27	35	74	52	57	109	671
	15	34	39	29	59	73	51	90	98	76	107	671
	17	63	71	49	88	93	83	32	46	24	105	671
	19	86	100	78	36	44	22	61	66	56	103	671
	112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

The blocks of order 8 are equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 10.

2.2 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 12

Below are three different ways of writing **block-wise** magic squares of order 12. First as magic square formed by 16 blocks of magic squares of order 3 with different magic sums. Second as magic square formed by 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums. Third as 4 blocks of order 6 with equal magic sums. In the first two cases, the magic square of order 12 is **pandiagonal**, while third case, it is just a magic square.

• Blocks of Order 3

12x12	pan	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
870	98	1	51	72	22	119	78	28	125	140	43	93	870
870	3	50	97	118	71	24	124	77	30	45	92	139	870
870	49	99	2	23	120	70	29	126	76	91	141	44	870
870	131	34	84	87	37	134	57	7	104	113	16	66	870
870	36	83	130	133	86	39	103	56	9	18	65	112	870
870	82	132	35	38	135	85	8	105	55	64	114	17	870
870	67	117	20	5	102	52	47	144	94	73	123	26	870
870	21	68	115	100	53	6	142	95	48	27	74	121	870
870	116	19	69	54	4	101	96	46	143	122	25	75	870
870	88	138	41	32	129	79	14	111	61	58	108	11	870
870	42	89	136	127	80	33	109	62	15	12	59	106	870
	137	40	90	81	31	128	63	13	110	107	10	60	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

• Blocks of Order 4

12x12	pan	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
870	7	140	1	142	15	132	9	134	23	124	17	126	870
870	2	141	8	139	10	133	16	131	18	125	24	123	870
870	144	3	138	5	136	11	130	13	128	19	122	21	870
870	137	6	143	4	129	14	135	12	121	22	127	20	870
870	31	116	25	118	39	108	33	110	47	100	41	102	870
870	26	117	32	115	34	109	40	107	42	101	48	99	870
870	120	27	114	29	112	35	106	37	104	43	98	45	870
870	113	30	119	28	105	38	111	36	97	46	103	44	870
870	55	92	49	94	63	84	57	86	71	76	65	78	870
870	50	93	56	91	58	85	64	83	66	77	72	75	870
870	96	51	90	53	88	59	82	61	80	67	74	69	870
	89	54	95	52	81	62	87	60	73	70	79	68	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

• Blocks of Order 6

12	mgc											870	
	1	143	142	141	2	6	19	125	124	123	20	24	870
	138	8	136	9	11	133	120	26	118	27	29	115	870
	132	131	15	16	128	13	114	113	33	34	110	31	870
	18	14	129	130	17	127	36	32	111	112	35	109	870
	7	134	10	135	137	12	25	116	28	117	119	30	870
	139	5	3	4	140	144	121	23	21	22	122	126	870
	55	89	88	87	56	60	37	107	106	105	38	42	870
	84	62	82	63	65	79	102	44	100	45	47	97	870
	78	77	69	70	74	67	96	95	51	52	92	49	870
	72	68	75	76	71	73	54	50	93	94	53	91	870
	61	80	64	81	83	66	43	98	46	99	101	48	870
	85	59	57	58	86	90	103	41	39	40	104	108	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

More on these kind of magic squares can be seen in author's work [26, 27, 28]. The aim of this work write magic squares with blocks of order 4 with distinct prime number entries.

Based on the idea of blocks, block-borders, etc. given above, we shall concentrate our work in this direction on **prime magic squares**. This whole work is given in many parts.

3 Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares of Order 6-14

This work brings different ways representing magic squares in prime numbers. Initial aim is represent in terms of blocks. Some of possibilities led us to concentric or single-layer bordered magic squares. It includes blocks of orders 3, 4, 5, etc. Sometimes these blocks are of **equal** or **different** magic sums. This work is for the orders 6 to 14. In case of order 10, 11, 13, 14, etc, we don't have division in blocks but we represent them as block-bordered. This means there are one or two layers of border, while the internal part is as blocks of small orders.

Whenever, we write **prime magic square**, it means that the magic squares are composed of **distinct prime number entries**, except in few cases, we the central constant 1000003 is repeating. This constant generally goes up to certain order, i.e, around order 120. For orders

higher than this, the next central constant is used. It is only in case of odd order primes magic squares.

For each order we worked with **different types of representations** of prime magic squares. Below is the list in each case.

Order	Representations
6	3
7	2
8	3
9	4
10	4
11	3
12	6
13	3
14	7

This work is specially for distinct prime numbers, except in some cases there are repetition of central values. For similar kind of work for sequential numbers entries, see the author’s work [21, 26, 27, 28] given in the reference list.

3.1 Prime Magic Squares of Order 6

Below are three examples of prime magic squares of order 6 with different representations.

Example 1. Prime Magic Square. *Let’s consider a following prime magic square:*

6	mgc						9064122
	1414801	1557797	1656847	1459873	1259903	1714901	9064122
	1364191	1660727	1693067	1343689	1758187	1244261	9064122
	1621619	1768141	1310963	1360027	1362401	1640971	9064122
	1485853	1568389	1231039	1663793	1474439	1640609	9064122
	213659	35969	172423	2939231	2946649	2756191	9064122
	2963999	2473099	2999783	297509	262543	67189	9064122
9064122	9064122	9064122	9064122	9064122	9064122	9064122	9064122

It is a general **prime magic square** without any specific properties.

Example 2. Single-Layer Bordered Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

6	mgc						6000018
	306049	1520509	328327	1552123	877873	1415137	6000018
	1168477	1335409	481693	1518313	664597	831529	6000018
	686437	980593	934693	1065313	1019413	1313569	6000018
	1504033	930547	1516639	483367	1069459	495973	6000018
	1750153	753463	1066987	933019	1246543	249853	6000018
	584869	479497	1671679	447883	1122133	1693957	6000018
	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018

It is **single-layer bordered prime magic square**. Sometimes it is called as **concentric**. The internal block is again a prime magic square of order 4. See below:

4	mgc					4000012
	1335409	481693	1518313	664597	4000012	
	980593	934693	1065313	1019413	4000012	
	930547	1516639	483367	1069459	4000012	
	753463	1066987	933019	1246543	4000012	
	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	

Example 3. Equal Sums Blocks Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

6	mgc						6000018
	1073713	584863	1341433	1412833	439459	1147717	6000018
	1267723	1000003	732283	734887	1000003	1265119	6000018
	658573	1415143	926293	852289	1560547	587173	6000018
	1154353	327343	1518313	1244863	293263	1461883	6000018
	1363963	1000003	636043	1217023	1000003	782983	6000018
	481693	1672663	845653	538123	1706743	755143	6000018
	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018

It is **block-wise prime magic square** composed of four **equal sums prime magic square** of order 3. The central prime number in each case 1000003 is repeated. This repetition allows us to have equal sums prime magic square of order 3. See below:

3	mgc			3000009	3	mgc			3000009
	1073713	584863	1341433	3000009		1412833	439459	1147717	3000009
	1267723	1000003	732283	3000009		734887	1000003	1265119	3000009
	658573	1415143	926293	3000009		852289	1560547	587173	3000009
	3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009
3	mgc			3000009	3	mgc			3000009
	1154353	327343	1518313	3000009		1244863	293263	1461883	3000009
	1363963	1000003	636043	3000009		1217023	1000003	782983	3000009
	481693	1672663	845653	3000009		538123	1706743	755143	3000009
	3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009

3.2 Prime Magic Squares of Order 7

Below are two examples of prime magic squares of order 7 with different representations.

Example 4. Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

7	mgc								11852197
	1616833	1956763	1598711	1446779	1743031	1937237	1552843		11852197
	1911109	1876289	1491437	1446073	1536989	1686511	1903789		11852197
	1723063	1487099	1780351	1785143	1592581	1592341	1891619		11852197
	1812623	1871263	1538011	1454569	1601627	1885423	1688681		11852197
	1671713	1952641	1421857	1821121	1572203	1740881	1671781		11852197
	239489	1266469	3154429	3170383	3119293	655301	246833		11852197
	2877367	1441673	867401	728129	686473	2354503	2896651		11852197
	11852197	11852197	11852197	11852197	11852197	11852197	11852197		11852197

It is a general **prime magic square** without any specific properties.

Example 5. Single-Layer Bordered Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

7	mgc							7000021
	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	7000021
	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	7000021
	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	7000021
	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	7000021
	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	7000021
	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	7000021
	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	7000021
	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021

It is **single-layer bordered prime magic square**. Sometimes it is called as **concentric**. The internal blocks are again a prime magic squares of orders 5 and 3. See below:

5	mgc						5000015					
	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	5000015	3	mgc				3000009
	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	5000015		999613	1004677	995719	3000009	
	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	5000015		996109	1000003	1003897	3000009	
	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	5000015		1004287	995329	1000393	3000009	
	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	5000015		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009	
	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015						

3.3 Prime Magic Squares of Order 8

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 8 with different representations.

Example 6. Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

8	mgc								17959064
	2182619	2396153	2134261	2286953	2255399	2391751	2343989	1967939	17959064
	2356597	2514529	2041661	2285291	2231711	2032307	2216057	2280911	17959064
	2175559	2320321	2187197	2255677	2043323	2461337	2398027	2117623	17959064
	2085133	2339929	2172829	2258299	2534867	2057639	1980821	2529547	17959064
	2426027	2385703	2364679	2294059	2266337	2028281	2186029	2007949	17959064
	2318483	2316331	2112347	2203711	2393473	2077987	2292463	2244269	17959064
	794389	752201	3711121	3613681	3433481	3718643	798409	1137139	17959064
	3620257	2933897	1234969	761393	800473	1191119	3743269	3673687	17959064
	17959064	17959064	17959064	17959064	17959064	17959064	17959064	17959064	17959064

It is a general **prime magic square** without any specific properties.

Example 7. Equal Sums Blocks Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

8	mgc								8000024
	1429369	983863	1016143	570637	580633	589759	1410247	1419373	8000024
	511507	1130023	869983	1488499	1025119	1269007	730999	974887	8000024
	950233	1450489	549517	1049773	810913	266293	1733713	1189093	8000024
	1108903	435637	1564369	891103	1583347	1874953	125053	416659	8000024
	1162339	1423369	576637	837667	430819	1049479	950527	1569187	8000024
	848227	528313	1471693	1151779	1288213	1594807	405199	711793	8000024
	1132927	834133	1165873	867079	980503	725149	1274857	1019503	8000024
	856519	1214197	785809	1143487	1300477	630577	1369429	699529	8000024
	8000024	8000024	8000024	8000024	8000024	8000024	8000024	8000024	8000024

It is **equal sum blocks prime magic square**. The four blocks of order 4 are prime magic squares. See below:

4	mgc					4000012	4	mgc					4000012
	1429369	983863	1016143	570637	4000012		580633	589759	1410247	1419373	4000012		
	511507	1130023	869983	1488499	4000012		1025119	1269007	730999	974887	4000012		
	950233	1450489	549517	1049773	4000012		810913	266293	1733713	1189093	4000012		
	1108903	435637	1564369	891103	4000012		1583347	1874953	125053	416659	4000012		
	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012		4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012		
4	mgc					4000012	4	mgc					4000012
	1162339	1423369	576637	837667	4000012		430819	1049479	950527	1569187	4000012		
	848227	528313	1471693	1151779	4000012		1288213	1594807	405199	711793	4000012		
	1132927	834133	1165873	867079	4000012		980503	725149	1274857	1019503	4000012		
	856519	1214197	785809	1143487	4000012		1300477	630577	1369429	699529	4000012		
	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012		4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012		

Example 8. Single-Layer Bordered Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

8	mgc								4000000
	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	4000000
	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	4000000
	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	4000000
	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	4000000
	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	4000000
	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	4000000
	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	4000000
	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	4000000
	4000000	4000000	4000000	4000000	4000000	4000000	4000000	4000000	4000000

It is **single-layer bordered prime magic square**. Sometimes it is called as **concentric**. The internal blocks are again a prime magic squares of orders 6 and 4. See below:

6	mgc						3000000							
	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	3000000	4	mgc					2000000
	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	3000000		306191	65951	934049	693809	2000000	
	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	3000000		878651	799619	200381	121349	2000000	
	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	3000000		517901	808553	191447	482099	2000000	
	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	3000000		297257	325877	674123	702743	2000000	
	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	3000000		2000000	2000000	2000000	2000000	2000000	
	3000000	3000000	3000000	3000000	3000000	3000000	3000000						2000000	

3.4 Prime Magic Squares of Order 9

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 9 with different representations.

Example 9. Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

9	mgc									6287877
	246217	164413	1148437	316087	810253	1200643	715153	528247	1158427	6287877
	793537	709909	475897	938713	241903	929239	913573	681337	603769	6287877
	794023	1061107	1058059	998749	229123	712417	494917	336199	603283	6287877
	622639	626377	927007	508513	439357	1148089	470299	770929	774667	6287877
	1071193	658153	147613	1338229	698653	59077	1249693	739153	326113	6287877
	1190899	737887	458197	249217	957949	888793	939109	659419	206407	6287877
	760477	381169	902389	398557	1168183	684889	339247	1016137	636829	6287877
	570013	715969	921409	458593	1155403	468067	483733	687397	827293	6287877
	238879	1232893	248869	1081219	587053	196663	682153	869059	1151089	6287877
	6287877	6287877	6287877	6287877	6287877	6287877	6287877	6287877	6287877	6287877

It is general prime magic square of order 9 without any special properties.

Example 10. Different Sums Blocks Primes Magic Square. *Let's consider a following prime magic square:*

9	mgc									677907
	64817	75983	79031	39359	86249	100829	39827	106619	85193	677907
	87491	73277	59063	136949	75479	14009	122579	77213	31847	677907
	67523	70571	81737	50129	64709	111599	69233	47807	114599	677907
	43049	79139	115589	66713	49823	109433	47507	67421	99233	677907
	151799	79259	6719	118043	75323	32603	123113	71387	19661	677907
	42929	79379	115469	41213	100823	83933	43541	75353	95267	677907
	40883	98927	80489	45641	101513	78347	53951	87917	90239	677907
	113039	73433	33827	107873	75167	42461	113657	77369	41081	677907
	66377	47939	105983	71987	48821	104693	64499	66821	100787	677907
	677907	677907	677907	677907	677907	677907	677907	677907	677907	677907

*It is a **block-wise prime magic square** of order 9 with 9 blocks of **different sums** prime magic square of order 3. See below few examples of order 3:*

3	mgc			219831	3	mgc			214161	3	mgc			231639
	64817	75983	79031	219831		47507	67421	99233	214161		39827	106619	85193	231639
	87491	73277	59063	219831		123113	71387	19661	214161		122579	77213	31847	231639
	67523	70571	81737	219831		43541	75353	95267	214161		69233	47807	114599	231639
	219831	219831	219831	219831		214161	214161	214161	214161		231639	231639	231639	231639
3	mgc			226437	3	mgc			232107	3	mgc			225501
	39359	86249	100829	226437		53951	87917	90239	232107		45641	101513	78347	225501
	136949	75479	14009	226437		113657	77369	41081	232107		107873	75167	42461	225501
	50129	64709	111599	226437		64499	66821	100787	232107		71987	48821	104693	225501
	226437	226437	226437	226437		232107	232107	232107	232107		225501	225501	225501	225501

Example 11. Equal Sums Blocks Primes Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

9	mgc													9000027
	868123	781003	1350883	760063	613969	1625977	1103863	1783219	112927	9000027				9000027
	1482763	1000003	517243	1865917	1000003	134089	9067	1000003	1990939	9000027				9000027
	649123	1219003	1131883	374029	1386037	1239943	1887079	216787	896143	9000027				9000027
	1089793	385417	1524799	711133	1972423	316453	1421473	664663	913873	9000027				9000027
	1435009	1000003	564997	605323	1000003	1394683	492403	1000003	1507603	9000027				9000027
	475207	1614589	910213	1683553	27583	1288873	1086133	1335343	578533	9000027				9000027
	1413103	636673	950233	1535959	290497	1173553	502057	1969069	528883	9000027				9000027
	537133	1000003	1462873	637597	1000003	1362409	1026829	1000003	973177	9000027				9000027
	1049773	1363333	586903	826453	1709509	464047	1471123	30937	1497949	9000027				9000027
	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027				9000027

It is a **block-wise prime magic square** of order 9 with 9 blocks of **equal sums** prime magic square of order 3. See below few examples of order 3:

3	mgc			3000009	3	mgc			3000009	3	mgc			3000009
	868123	781003	1350883	3000009		1421473	664663	913873	3000009		711133	1972423	316453	3000009
	1482763	1000003	517243	3000009		492403	1000003	1507603	3000009		605323	1000003	1394683	3000009
	649123	1219003	1131883	3000009		1086133	1335343	578533	3000009		1683553	27583	1288873	3000009
	3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009
3	mgc			3000009	3	mgc			3000009	3	mgc			3000009
	1535959	290497	1173553	3000009		760063	613969	1625977	3000009		502057	1969069	528883	3000009
	637597	1000003	1362409	3000009		1865917	1000003	134089	3000009		1026829	1000003	973177	3000009
	826453	1709509	464047	3000009		374029	1386037	1239943	3000009		1471123	30937	1497949	3000009
	3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009

It is a **block-wise prime magic square** of order 9 with 9 blocks of **equal sums** magic square of order 3. In center of each block of order 3 there is a fixed prime number 100003. It makes easy to bring equal sums prime magic squares of odd orders.

Example 12. Single-Layer Bordered Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

9	mgc									9000027
	812167	586129	816037	972319	614527	579907	1225723	1898539	1494679	9000027
	986113	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	1013893	9000027
	93889	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	1906117	9000027
	614893	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	1385113	9000027
	427417	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	1572589	9000027
	1834663	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	165343	9000027
	1934389	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	65617	9000027
	1791169	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	208837	9000027
	505327	1413877	1183969	1027687	1385479	1420099	774283	101467	1187839	9000027
	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027

It is **single-layer bordered prime magic square**. Sometimes it is called as **concentric**. The internal blocks are again a prime magic squares of orders 7, 5 and 3. It is the same as given in Example 5.

3.5 Prime Magic Squares of Order 10

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 10 with different representations.

Example 13. Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

10	mgc										16150730
	1369321	1374677	1510961	1791091	1486403	1533643	1841923	1698127	1873133	1671451	16150730
	1534667	1662347	1610443	1884677	1610533	1688651	1374301	1775261	1431047	1578803	16150730
	1909087	1424699	1484051	1647931	1454533	1791463	1595749	1530077	1422133	1891007	16150730
	1644607	1420253	1540997	1757677	1395859	1884611	1454143	1791739	1662503	1598341	16150730
	1675291	1402571	1571833	1387151	1867157	1543537	1651219	1482193	1827799	1741979	16150730
	1347211	1871083	1435921	1877669	1654981	1422119	1561117	1597931	1714667	1668031	16150730
	1863053	1860163	1614593	1330603	1483171	1374341	1830079	1519759	1571411	1703557	16150730
	1571183	1451053	1702991	1692541	1703323	1343887	1893361	1793369	1339853	1659169	16150730
	126473	722063	3031841	2662841	3080303	2999047	2810369	125497	459257	133039	16150730
	3109837	2961821	647099	118549	414467	569431	138469	2836777	2848927	2505353	16150730
	16150730	16150730	16150730	16150730	16150730	16150730	16150730	16150730	16150730	16150730	16150730

It is general prime magic square of order 10 without any special properties.

Example 14. Block-Bordered Nested Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

10	mgc										10000030
	1899673	1464049	853873	1106779	840163	678739	362977	1310077	1370263	113437	10000030
	1022377	1429369	983863	1016143	570637	580633	589759	1410247	1419373	977629	10000030
	769627	511507	1130023	869983	1488499	1025119	1269007	730999	974887	1230379	10000030
	478243	950233	1450489	549517	1049773	810913	266293	1733713	1189093	1521763	10000030
	339799	1108903	435637	1564369	891103	1583347	1874953	125053	416659	1660207	10000030
	1170553	1162339	1423369	576637	837667	430819	1049479	950527	1569187	829453	10000030
	704017	848227	528313	1471693	1151779	1288213	1594807	405199	711793	1295989	10000030
	1067509	1132927	834133	1165873	867079	980503	725149	1274857	1019503	932497	10000030
	661663	856519	1214197	785809	1143487	1300477	630577	1369429	699529	1338343	10000030
	1886569	535957	1146133	893227	1159843	1321267	1637029	689929	629743	100333	10000030
	10000030	10000030	10000030	10000030	10000030	10000030	10000030	10000030	10000030	10000030	10000030

It is a **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 10. The internal part is a magic square of order 8 composed of 4 **equal sums** prime magic squares of order 4. It is the same example as given Example 7.

Example 15. Equal Sum Blocks Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

10	mgc										10000030
	1125907	1059637	394837	1151167	1268467	912103	1343257	1172659	305839	1266157	10000030
	1557769	1068589	790927	1140493	442237	1633837	1351663	581947	1066399	366169	10000030
	418927	1071907	1000003	928099	1581079	1347457	714739	1000003	1285267	652549	10000030
	1165873	859513	1209079	931417	834133	372769	933607	1418059	648343	1627237	10000030
	731539	940369	1605169	848839	874099	733849	656749	827347	1694167	1087903	10000030
	1025257	349849	1633573	1560883	430453	798097	1335409	651067	1224919	990523	10000030
	278623	1741603	263827	994579	1721383	727123	1122133	529813	1348063	1272883	10000030
	1068619	252979	1000003	1747027	931387	1627729	1225933	1000003	774073	372277	10000030
	1057963	1005427	1736179	258403	942043	837583	651943	1470193	877873	1162423	10000030
	1569553	1650157	366433	439123	974749	1009483	664597	1348939	775087	1201909	10000030
	10000030	10000030	10000030	10000030	10000030	10000030	10000030	10000030	10000030	10000030	10000030

It is **equal sum block prime magic square** of order 10 composed of four equal sums **single-layer bordered** prime magic squares of order 5. See below two examples:

3	mgc				3000009
	1068589	790927	1140493		3000009
	1071907	1000003	928099		3000009
	859513	1209079	931417		3000009
	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009

3	mgc				3000009
	1741603	263827	994579		3000009
	252979	1000003	1747027		3000009
	1005427	1736179	258403		3000009
	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009

5	mgc					5000015
	1125907	1059637	394837	1151167	1268467	5000015
	1557769	1068589	790927	1140493	442237	5000015
	418927	1071907	1000003	928099	1581079	5000015
	1165873	859513	1209079	931417	834133	5000015
	731539	940369	1605169	848839	874099	5000015
	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015

5	mgc					5000015
	1025257	349849	1633573	1560883	430453	5000015
	278623	1741603	263827	994579	1721383	5000015
	1068619	252979	1000003	1747027	931387	5000015
	1057963	1005427	1736179	258403	942043	5000015
	1569553	1650157	366433	439123	974749	5000015
	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015

Example 16. Single-Layer Bordered Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

10	mgc										5000000
	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	5000000
	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	5000000
	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	5000000
	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	5000000
	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	5000000
	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	5000000
	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	5000000
	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	5000000
	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	5000000
	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	5000000
	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000	5000000

It is **single-layer bordered prime magic square**. Sometimes it is called as **concentric**. The internal blocks are again a prime magic squares of orders 8, 6 and 4. See below:

8	mgc								4000000															
	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	4000000	6	mgc						3000000							
	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	4000000		881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	3000000	4	mgc					2000000
	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	4000000		149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	3000000		306191	65951	934049	693809	2000000	
	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	4000000		194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	3000000		878651	799619	200381	121349	2000000	
	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	4000000		349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	3000000		517901	808553	191447	482099	2000000	
	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	4000000		933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	3000000		297257	325877	674123	702743	2000000	
	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	4000000		491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	3000000		2000000	2000000	2000000	2000000	2000000	
	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	4000000		3000000	3000000	3000000	3000000	3000000	3000000	3000000							
	4000000	4000000	4000000	4000000	4000000	4000000	4000000	4000000	4000000															

3.6 Prime Magic Squares of Order 11

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 11 with different representations.

Example 17. Block-Bordred Nested Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

11	mgc											24563429
	345139	422029	555967	2074141	398611	3622951	2166691	4246057	4377757	4436119	1917967	24563429
	270217	1621861	1172107	2458039	1194157	1168987	2017987	2187511	4752133	3524569	4195861	24563429
	2024647	2586847	1750669	914491	2284207	1460377	636547	4825129	3488071	2151013	2441431	24563429
	351427	1043299	2329231	1879477	902767	1751767	1726597	3451573	2224009	4788631	4114651	24563429
	120049	3409711	3667621	4833991	1496149	2546239	2656729	324763	609751	552397	4346029	24563429
	3920551	5394721	3970441	2546161	3393619	2233039	1072459	723271	495637	268003	545527	24563429
	3607837	3106891	4273261	4531171	1809349	1919839	2969929	438877	381523	666511	858241	24563429
	2641351	577453	941251	1415317	1821709	4050433	3144961	2172817	2183131	3790279	1824727	24563429
	4404469	1815871	978007	140143	4328953	3005701	1682449	4332871	2715409	1097947	61609	24563429
	4329631	540697	1014763	1378561	2866441	1960969	4189693	1640539	3247687	3258001	136447	24563429
	2548111	4044049	3910111	2391937	4067467	843127	2299387	220021	88321	29959	4120939	24563429
	24563429	24563429	24563429	24563429	24563429	24563429	24563429	24563429	24563429	24563429	24563429	24563429

It is a **block-bordered prime magic square** with inner part as a prime magic square of order 9. It is composed of 9 **different sums** magic squares of order 3. It is the same example as given in Example 10.

Example 18. Block-Bordred Nested Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

11	mgc											11000033
	721843	501463	310789	4219	860323	906679	603283	1992637	1998943	1934887	1164967	11000033
	754903	868123	781003	1350883	760063	613969	1625977	1103863	1783219	112927	1245103	11000033
	707467	1482763	1000003	517243	1865917	1000003	134089	9067	1000003	1990939	1292539	11000033
	571069	649123	1219003	1131883	374029	1386037	1239943	1887079	216787	896143	1428937	11000033
	410953	1089793	385417	1524799	711133	1972423	316453	1421473	664663	913873	1589053	11000033
	357913	1435009	1000003	564997	605323	1000003	1394683	492403	1000003	1507603	1642093	11000033
	1677037	475207	1614589	910213	1683553	27583	1288873	1086133	1335343	578533	322969	11000033
	1126537	1413103	636673	950233	1535959	290497	1173553	502057	1969069	528883	873469	11000033
	1927963	537133	1000003	1462873	637597	1000003	1362409	1026829	1000003	973177	72043	11000033
	1909309	1049773	1363333	586903	826453	1709509	464047	1471123	30937	1497949	90697	11000033
	835039	1498543	1689217	1995787	1139683	1093327	1396723	7369	1063	65119	1278163	11000033
	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033

It is a **block-bordered prime magic square** with inner part as a prime magic square of order 9. It is composed of 9 **equal sums** magic squares of order 3. It is the same example as given in Example 11.

Example 19. Single-Layer Bordered Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

11	mgc											11000033
	721843	501463	310789	4219	860323	906679	603283	1992637	1998943	1934887	1164967	11000033
	754903	812167	586129	816037	972319	614527	579907	1225723	1898539	1494679	1245103	11000033
	707467	986113	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	1013893	1292539	11000033
	571069	93889	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	1906117	1428937	11000033
	410953	614893	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	1385113	1589053	11000033
	357913	427417	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	1572589	1642093	11000033
	1677037	1834663	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	165343	322969	11000033
	1126537	1934389	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	65617	873469	11000033
	1927963	1791169	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	208837	72043	11000033
	1909309	505327	1413877	1183969	1027687	1385479	1420099	774283	101467	1187839	90697	11000033
	835039	1498543	1689217	1995787	1139683	1093327	1396723	7369	1063	65119	1278163	11000033
	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033

It is **single-layer bordered prime magic square**. Sometimes it is called as **concentric**. The internal blocks are again a prime magic squares of orders 9, 7, 5 and 3. It is the same prime magic square of order 9 as given in Example 12.

3.7 Prime Magic Squares of Order 12

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 12 with different representations.

Example 20. Different Sums Blocks Prime Magic Square Let's consider a following prime magic square:

12	mgc												24000000	
		1227143	1976657	2046959	1033069	1807921	2734117	1248829	3479557	2669581	1019449	2380801	2375917	24000000
		2570069	1750253	930437	3559417	1858369	157321	3886741	2465989	1045237	3281857	1925389	568921	24000000
		1453547	1523849	2273363	982621	1908817	2683669	2262397	1452421	3683149	1474861	1469977	2831329	24000000
		2305777	1276243	3507481	1556323	2286847	1925779	978463	1386193	1927483	1462037	1965077	3422297	24000000
		3564871	2363167	1161463	2292439	1922983	1553527	2379733	1430713	481693	4243397	2283137	322877	24000000
		1218853	3450091	2420557	1920187	1559119	2289643	933943	1475233	1882963	1143977	2601197	3104237	24000000
		1258819	2139661	2349337	1906271	3128393	2985107	1820617	1718551	2379973	1322227	1009627	1981417	24000000
		3006457	1915939	825421	3752093	2673257	1594421	2532403	1973047	1413691	2096947	1437757	778567	24000000
		1482541	1692217	2573059	2361407	2218121	3440243	1566121	2227543	2125477	894097	1865887	1553287	24000000
		1358881	2147059	2405983	1103101	1404973	2128099	1228181	2325623	2836949	2243317	1989241	2828593	24000000
		3017743	1970641	923539	2570389	1545391	520393	3739019	2130251	521483	2938993	2353717	1768441	24000000
		1535299	1794223	2582401	962683	1685809	1987681	1423553	1934879	3032321	1878841	2718193	2464117	24000000
		24000000	24000000	24000000	24000000	24000000	24000000	24000000	24000000	24000000	24000000	24000000	24000000	24000000

It is a **block-wise prime magic square** of order 12 with 16 blocks of **different sums prime magic square** of order 3. See below few examples of order 3. See few examples of prime magic squares of order 3:

3	mgc				5250759	3	mgc				5575107	3	mgc				7397967
		1227143	1976657	2046959	5250759			1033069	1807921	2734117	5575107			1248829	3479557	2669581	7397967
		2570069	1750253	930437	5250759			3559417	1858369	157321	5575107			3886741	2465989	1045237	7397967
		1453547	1523849	2273363	5250759			982621	1908817	2683669	5575107			2262397	1452421	3683149	7397967
		5250759	5250759	5250759	5250759			5575107	5575107	5575107	5575107			7397967	7397967	7397967	7397967
3	mgc				7089501	3	mgc				5768949	3	mgc				4292139
		2305777	1276243	3507481	7089501			1556323	2286847	1925779	5768949			978463	1386193	1927483	4292139
		3564871	2363167	1161463	7089501			2292439	1922983	1553527	5768949			2379733	1430713	481693	4292139
		1218853	3450091	2420557	7089501			1920187	1559119	2289643	5768949			933943	1475233	1882963	4292139
		7089501	7089501	7089501	7089501			5768949	5768949	5768949	5768949			4292139	4292139	4292139	4292139

Example 21. Equal Sums Blocks Prime Magic Square Let's consider a following prime magic square:

12	mgc												12000036
	424819	1788037	787153	101749	1943827	954433	840943	1998133	160933	1343983	822517	833509	12000036
	1362337	1000003	637669	1852687	1000003	147319	319993	1000003	1680013	489529	1000003	1510477	12000036
	1212853	211969	1575187	1045573	56179	1898257	1839073	1873	1159063	1166497	1177489	656023	12000036
	1200673	1122739	676597	606673	1738783	654553	961879	222067	1816063	1308943	89413	1601653	12000036
	475927	1000003	1524079	1047883	1000003	952123	1854187	1000003	145819	1292713	1000003	707293	12000036
	1323409	877267	799333	1345453	261223	1393333	183943	1777939	1038127	398353	1910593	691063	12000036
	1224859	433267	1341883	553933	1514659	931417	303679	1528237	1168093	682483	1968817	348709	12000036
	1117027	1000003	882979	1377487	1000003	622519	1864417	1000003	135589	666229	1000003	1333777	12000036
	658123	1566739	775147	1068589	485347	1446073	831913	471769	1696327	1651297	31189	1317523	12000036
	734143	1588183	677683	596839	1813387	589783	1084459	1815817	99733	374299	1928947	696763	12000036
	943543	1000003	1056463	992947	1000003	1007059	15277	1000003	1984729	1322467	1000003	677539	12000036
	1322323	411823	1265863	1410223	186619	1403167	1900273	184189	915547	1303243	71059	1625707	12000036
	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036

It is a **block-wise prime magic square** of order 12 with 16 blocks of **equal sums prime magic square** of order 3. See below few examples of order 3. See few examples of prime magic squares of order 3:

3	mgc				3000009	3	mgc				3000009	3	mgc				3000009
	424819	1788037	787153	3000009			840943	1998133	160933	3000009			1343983	822517	833509	3000009	
	1362337	1000003	637669	3000009			319993	1000003	1680013	3000009			489529	1000003	1510477	3000009	
	1212853	211969	1575187	3000009			1839073	1873	1159063	3000009			1166497	1177489	656023	3000009	
	3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009			3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009			3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009	
3	mgc				3000009	3	mgc				3000009	3	mgc				3000009
	596839	1813387	589783	3000009			303679	1528237	1168093	3000009			374299	1928947	696763	3000009	
	992947	1000003	1007059	3000009			1864417	1000003	135589	3000009			1322467	1000003	677539	3000009	
	1410223	186619	1403167	3000009			831913	471769	1696327	3000009			1303243	71059	1625707	3000009	
	3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009			3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009			3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009	

Example 22. Different Sums Blocks Prime Magic Square Let's consider a following prime magic square:

12	mgc												25156524
	1298027	2293883	1550567	2039671	2032687	2101483	2364727	2483827	2013119	1847357	2542999	2588177	25156524
	1737523	1241699	1959593	2243333	2384653	2386861	2397049	1814161	1867913	2282149	2365469	2476121	25156524
	2348441	1384727	2596129	852851	1924033	1460497	2738317	2859877	2165921	1093307	3250727	2481697	25156524
	1798157	2261839	1075859	2046293	2641351	3033883	1482631	1824859	2944699	3768839	832457	1445657	25156524
	2520577	2090219	2963333	2620883	2247851	2585417	1616623	1935617	1817801	1081793	2045567	1630843	25156524
	2028263	2536307	2612131	3018311	2217217	1653251	2561729	1953311	1282451	1516687	1883393	1893473	25156524
	2946611	2262437	2784137	2201827	1809887	1777609	2392919	2405093	2159881	1745897	1430027	1240199	25156524
	2699561	3306049	1835411	2353991	2110553	2369231	1814237	2091487	1315871	2231627	1217017	1811489	25156524
	2019569	2082539	1518563	2158693	2179327	2506547	1688741	1413677	2859137	2098697	2322797	2308237	25156524
	2357923	1466243	1993067	1962131	2221403	1458071	1685911	2422907	2634319	2493347	2097803	2363399	25156524
	1692161	1917893	2402161	1767149	1724981	3026123	1618187	1419001	2427281	3514697	1483021	2163869	25156524
	1709711	2312689	1865573	1891391	1662581	797551	2795453	2532707	1668131	1482127	3685247	2753363	25156524
	25156524	25156524	25156524	25156524	25156524	25156524	25156524	25156524	25156524	25156524	25156524	25156524	25156524

It is a **block-wise prime magic square** of order 12 with 9 blocks of **different sums prime magic square** of order 3. See below few examples of order 3. See few examples of prime magic squares of order 3:

4	mgc					7182148	4	mgc					8982724	4	mgc					8991652
	1298027	2293883	1550567	2039671	7182148			2032687	2101483	2364727	2483827	8982724			2013119	1847357	2542999	2588177	8991652	
	1737523	1241699	1959593	2243333	7182148			2384653	2386861	2397049	1814161	8982724			1867913	2282149	2365469	2476121	8991652	
	2348441	1384727	2596129	852851	7182148			1924033	1460497	2738317	2859877	8982724			2165921	1093307	3250727	2481697	8991652	
	1798157	2261839	1075859	2046293	7182148			2641351	3033883	1482631	1824859	8982724			2944699	3768839	832457	1445657	8991652	
	7182148	7182148	7182148	7182148	7182148			8982724	8982724	8982724	8982724	8982724			8991652	8991652	8991652	8991652	8991652	
4	mgc					10195012	4	mgc					8385508	4	mgc					6576004
	2520577	2090219	2963333	2620883	10195012			2247851	2585417	1616623	1935617	8385508			1817801	1081793	2045567	1630843	6576004	
	2028263	2536307	2612131	3018311	10195012			2217217	1653251	2561729	1953311	8385508			1282451	1516687	1883393	1893473	6576004	
	2946611	2262437	2784137	2201827	10195012			1809887	1777609	2392919	2405093	8385508			2159881	1745897	1430027	1240199	6576004	
	2699561	3306049	1835411	2353991	10195012			2110553	2369231	1814237	2091487	8385508			1315871	2231627	1217017	1811489	6576004	
	10195012	10195012	10195012	10195012	10195012			8385508	8385508	8385508	8385508	8385508			6576004	6576004	6576004	6576004	6576004	

Example 23. Equal Sums Blocks Prime Magic Square Let's consider a following prime magic square:

12	mgc												12000036
	1688179	307669	1692337	311827	1693303	309223	1690783	306703	1695283	310729	1689277	304723	12000036
	315517	1998397	1609	1684489	313333	1993273	6733	1686673	314239	1991293	8713	1685767	12000036
	733	1690993	309013	1999273	439	1693639	306367	1999567	457	1696543	303463	1999549	12000036
	1995583	2953	1997053	4423	1992937	3877	1996129	7069	1990033	1447	1998559	9973	12000036
	1294123	706633	1293373	705883	1299583	706267	1293739	700423	1306519	710293	1289713	693487	12000036
	710257	1994479	5527	1289749	707467	1989019	10987	1292539	695917	1982083	17923	1304089	12000036
	3643	1296613	703393	1996363	4993	1300633	699373	1995013	15823	1306849	693157	1984183	12000036
	1991989	2287	1997719	8017	1987969	4093	1995913	12037	1981753	787	1999219	18253	12000036
	1174759	836449	1163557	825247	1113877	893029	1106977	886129	1125127	897469	1102537	874879	12000036
	831367	1977817	22189	1168639	906649	1974787	25219	1093357	905449	1963537	36469	1094557	12000036
	19483	1178173	821833	1980523	14629	1123807	876199	1985377	10729	1129957	870049	1989277	12000036
	1974403	7573	1992433	25603	1964857	8389	1991617	35149	1958707	9049	1990957	41299	12000036
	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036

It is a **block-wise prime magic square** of order 12 with 9 blocks of **equal sums prime magic square** of order 4. See below few examples of order 4. See few examples of prime magic squares of order 4:

4	mgc					4000012	4	mgc					4000012	4	mgc					4000012
	1688179	307669	1692337	311827	4000012		1113877	893029	1106977	886129	4000012		1299583	706267	1293739	700423	4000012			
	315517	1998397	1609	1684489	4000012		906649	1974787	25219	1093357	4000012		707467	1989019	10987	1292539	4000012			
	733	1690993	309013	1999273	4000012		14629	1123807	876199	1985377	4000012		4993	1300633	699373	1995013	4000012			
	1995583	2953	1997053	4423	4000012		1964857	8389	1991617	35149	4000012		1987969	4093	1995913	12037	4000012			
	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012		4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012		4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012		
4	mgc					4000012	4	mgc					4000012	4	mgc					4000012
	1294123	706633	1293373	705883	4000012		1695283	310729	1689277	304723	4000012		1306519	710293	1289713	693487	4000012			
	710257	1994479	5527	1289749	4000012		314239	1991293	8713	1685767	4000012		695917	1982083	17923	1304089	4000012			
	3643	1296613	703393	1996363	4000012		457	1696543	303463	1999549	4000012		15823	1306849	693157	1984183	4000012			
	1991989	2287	1997719	8017	4000012		1990033	1447	1998559	9973	4000012		1981753	787	1999219	18253	4000012			
	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012		4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012		4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012		

Example 24. Equal Sums Blocks Prime Magic Square Let's consider a following prime magic square:

12	mgc												12000036
	306049	1520509	328327	1552123	877873	1415137	1299379	715237	1429543	422869	1488337	644653	12000036
	1168477	1335409	481693	1518313	664597	831529	1234837	1407619	521743	1478263	592387	765169	12000036
	686437	980593	934693	1065313	1019413	1313569	1537279	613507	1280473	719533	1386499	462727	12000036
	1504033	930547	1516639	483367	1069459	495973	492853	516673	1225879	774127	1483333	1507153	12000036
	1750153	753463	1066987	933019	1246543	249853	80317	1462213	971917	1028089	537793	1919689	12000036
	584869	479497	1671679	447883	1122133	1693957	1355353	1284769	570463	1577137	511669	700627	12000036
	1865917	358447	672223	1407877	1482457	213097	214237	942013	1458463	330859	1302739	1751707	12000036
	310789	1449979	566947	1433059	550027	1689217	1258753	1587973	660277	1339729	412033	741253	12000036
	1328749	477847	980557	1019449	1522159	671257	879283	826723	1348129	651877	1173283	1120723	12000036
	511867	1197649	1555999	444007	802357	1488139	1461283	621337	1972123	27883	1378669	538723	12000036
	195787	874537	896509	1103497	1125469	1804219	1938163	963979	19483	1980523	1036027	61843	12000036
	1786909	1641559	1327783	592129	517549	134089	248299	1057993	541543	1669147	697267	1785769	12000036
	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036	12000036

It is a **block-wise prime magic square** of order 12 with 4 blocks of **equal sums prime magic square** of order 6. See below few examples of order 6. See few examples of prime magic squares of order 6:

4	mgc					4000012					4	mgc					4000012		
	1335409	481693	1518313	664597	4000012						1407619	521743	1478263	592387	4000012				
	980593	934693	1065313	1019413	4000012						613507	1280473	719533	1386499	4000012				
	930547	1516639	483367	1069459	4000012						516673	1225879	774127	1483333	4000012				
	753463	1066987	933019	1246543	4000012						1462213	971917	1028089	537793	4000012				
	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012						4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012				
6	mgc						6000018					6	mgc						6000018
	306049	1520509	328327	1552123	877873	1415137	6000018					1299379	715237	1429543	422869	1488337	644653	6000018	
	1168477	1335409	481693	1518313	664597	831529	6000018					1234837	1407619	521743	1478263	592387	765169	6000018	
	686437	980593	934693	1065313	1019413	1313569	6000018					1537279	613507	1280473	719533	1386499	462727	6000018	
	1504033	930547	1516639	483367	1069459	495973	6000018					492853	516673	1225879	774127	1483333	1507153	6000018	
	1750153	753463	1066987	933019	1246543	249853	6000018					80317	1462213	971917	1028089	537793	1919689	6000018	
	584869	479497	1671679	447883	1122133	1693957	6000018					1355353	1284769	570463	1577137	511669	700627	6000018	
	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018					6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	

Example 25. Single-Layer Bordered Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

12	mgc												6000000
	109001	192617	318161	246473	173429	133877	460829	836117	948581	996323	975083	609509	6000000
	22643	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	977357	6000000
	70997	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	929003	6000000
	352511	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	647489	6000000
	120299	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	879701	6000000
	65921	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	934079	6000000
	989939	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	10061	6000000
	919823	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	80177	6000000
	963701	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	36299	6000000
	997793	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	2207	6000000
	996881	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	3119	6000000
	390491	807383	681839	753527	826571	866123	539171	163883	51419	3677	24917	890999	6000000
	6000000	6000000	6000000	6000000	6000000	6000000	6000000	6000000	6000000	6000000	6000000	6000000	6000000

It is **single-layer bordered prime magic square**. Sometimes it is called as **concentric**. The internal blocks are again a prime magic squares of orders 10, 8, 6 and 4. It is the same prime magic square of order 10 as given in Example 15.

3.8 Prime Magic Squares of Order 13

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 13 with different representations.

Example 26. Block-Bordred Nested Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

13	mgc													29029507
	3539917	2074081	3716821	2140267	340657	3157657	3271117	82837	764041	706117	4278049	4337569	620377	29029507
	972661	2198881	3610081	3905191	1656367	220537	2272657	4112917	1071487	2575549	613741	2326021	3493417	29029507
	2359789	1267237	1621861	1172107	2458039	1194157	1168987	2017987	2187511	4752133	3524569	3198841	2106289	29029507
	405829	2166289	2586847	1750669	914491	2284207	1460377	636547	4825129	3488071	2151013	2299789	4060249	29029507
	1655821	3240169	1043299	2329231	1879477	902767	1751767	1726597	3451573	2224009	4788631	1225909	2810257	29029507
	1504297	2519131	3409711	3667621	4833991	1496149	2546239	2656729	324763	609751	552397	1946947	2961781	29029507
	1499167	2765641	5394721	3970441	2546161	3393619	2233039	1072459	723271	495637	268003	1700437	2966911	29029507
	3307807	2772829	3106891	4273261	4531171	1809349	1919839	2969929	438877	381523	666511	1693249	1158271	29029507
	3128101	3563851	577453	941251	1415317	1821709	4050433	3144961	2172817	2183131	3790279	902227	1337977	29029507
	1156711	1075507	1815871	978007	140143	4328953	3005701	1682449	4332871	2715409	1097947	3390571	3309367	29029507
	3968227	853837	540697	1014763	1378561	2866441	1960969	4189693	1640539	3247687	3258001	3612241	497851	29029507
	1685479	2140057	855997	560887	2809711	4245541	2193421	353161	3394591	1890529	3852337	2267197	2780599	29029507
	3845701	2391997	749257	2325811	4125421	1308421	1194961	4383241	3702037	3759961	188029	128509	926161	29029507
	29029507	29029507	29029507	29029507	29029507	29029507	29029507	29029507	29029507	29029507	29029507	29029507	29029507	29029507

It is a **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 13, where the internal block of order 9 with **different blocks of primes magic squares of order 3** is as given in Example 10 Moreover, the internal prime magic square of order 11 is the same as given in Example 17

Example 27. Block-Bordred Nested Prime Magic Square.Let's consider a following prime magic square:

13	mgc													13000039
	2953	63607	611587	519433	734887	327343	769807	215983	1890103	1978993	1997467	1971127	1916749	13000039
	230143	721843	501463	310789	4219	860323	906679	603283	1992637	1998943	1934887	1164967	1769863	13000039
	536059	754903	868123	781003	1350883	760063	613969	1625977	1103863	1783219	112927	1245103	1463947	13000039
	76873	707467	1482763	1000003	517243	1865917	1000003	134089	9067	1000003	1990939	1292539	1923133	13000039
	418357	571069	649123	1219003	1131883	374029	1386037	1239943	1887079	216787	896143	1428937	1581649	13000039
	429277	410953	1089793	385417	1524799	711133	1972423	316453	1421473	664663	913873	1589053	1570729	13000039
	1968829	357913	1435009	1000003	564997	605323	1000003	1394683	492403	1000003	1507603	1642093	31177	13000039
	1864399	1677037	475207	1614589	910213	1683553	27583	1288873	1086133	1335343	578533	322969	135607	13000039
	1445929	1126537	1413103	636673	950233	1535959	290497	1173553	502057	1969069	528883	873469	554077	13000039
	1969153	1927963	537133	1000003	1462873	637597	1000003	1362409	1026829	1000003	973177	72043	30853	13000039
	1999567	1909309	1049773	1363333	586903	826453	1709509	464047	1471123	30937	1497949	90697	439	13000039
	1975243	835039	1498543	1689217	1995787	1139683	1093327	1396723	7369	1063	65119	1278163	24763	13000039
	83257	1936399	1388419	1480573	1265119	1672663	1230199	1784023	109903	21013	2539	28879	1997053	13000039
	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039

It is a **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 13, where the internal block of order 9 with **equal sum blocks of primes magic squares of order 3** is as given in Example 11 Moreover, the internal prime magic square of order 11 is the same as given in Example 18

Example 28. Single-Layer Bordered Prime Magic Square.Let's consider a following prime magic square:

13	mgc												9082489	
	817123	726007	550909	1020109	254389	1173343	685513	1179337	1020667	250057	215689	596749	592597	9082489
	658663	1227277	329089	153523	532999	234799	1202329	1076107	1055737	398863	1183447	291013	738643	9082489
	786337	145879	246217	164413	1148437	316087	810253	1200643	715153	528247	1158427	1251427	610969	9082489
	441187	1224703	793537	709909	475897	938713	241903	929239	913573	681337	603769	172603	956119	9082489
	566719	870097	794023	1061107	1058059	998749	229123	712417	494917	336199	603283	527209	830587	9082489
	904903	188473	622639	626377	927007	508513	439357	1148089	470299	770929	774667	1208833	492403	9082489
	901717	1189633	1071193	658153	147613	1338229	698653	59077	1249693	739153	326113	207673	495589	9082489
	720319	388933	1190899	737887	458197	249217	957949	888793	939109	659419	206407	1008373	676987	9082489
	1017673	676363	760477	381169	902389	398557	1168183	684889	339247	1016137	636829	720943	379633	9082489
	284407	145603	570013	715969	921409	458593	1155403	468067	483733	687397	827293	1251703	1112899	9082489
	174613	521929	238879	1232893	248869	1081219	587053	196663	682153	869059	1151089	875377	1222693	9082489
	1004119	1106293	1068217	1243783	864307	1162507	194977	321199	341569	998443	213859	170029	393187	9082489
	804709	671299	846397	377197	1142917	223963	711793	217969	376639	1147249	1181617	800557	580183	9082489
	9082489	9082489	9082489	9082489	9082489	9082489	9082489	9082489	9082489	9082489	9082489	9082489	9082489	9082489

It is **single-layer bordered prime magic square**. Sometimes it is called as **concentric**. The internal blocks are again a prime magic squares of orders 11, 9, 7, 5 and 3. It is the same prime magic square of order 11 as given in Example 19.

3.9 Prime Magic Squares of Order 14

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 14 with different representations.

Example 29. Block-Bordred Nested Prime Magic Square.Let's consider a following prime magic square:

14	mgc													28000000	
	715193	1365869	1879421	602033	322709	336689	501257	1678757	1808627	3992207	3996077	3999647	3999917	2801597	28000000
	893213	1227143	1976657	2046959	1033069	1807921	2734117	1248829	3479557	2669581	1019449	2380801	2375917	3106787	28000000
	241811	2570069	1750253	930437	3559417	1858369	157321	3886741	2465989	1045237	3281857	1925389	568921	3758189	28000000
	344291	1453547	1523849	2273363	982621	1908817	2683669	2262397	1452421	3683149	1474861	1469977	2831329	3655709	28000000
	787361	2305777	1276243	3507481	1556323	2286847	1925779	978463	1386193	1927483	1462037	1965077	3422297	3212639	28000000
	1036667	3564871	2363167	1161463	2292439	1922983	1553527	2379733	1430713	481693	4243397	2283137	322877	2963333	28000000
	1670531	1218853	3450091	2420557	1920187	1559119	2289643	933943	1475233	1882963	1143977	2601197	3104237	2329469	28000000
	1719143	1258819	2139661	2349337	1906271	3128393	2985107	1820617	1718551	2379973	1322227	1009627	1981417	2280857	28000000
	3878051	3006457	1915939	825421	3752093	2673257	1594421	2532403	1973047	1413691	2096947	1437757	778567	121949	28000000
	3589589	1482541	1692217	2573059	2361407	2218121	3440243	1566121	2227543	2125477	894097	1865887	1553287	410411	28000000
	3979739	1358881	2147059	2405983	1103101	1404973	2128099	1228181	2325623	2836949	2243317	1989241	2828593	20261	28000000
	3990281	3017743	1970641	923539	2570389	1545391	520393	3739019	2130251	521483	2938993	2353717	1768441	9719	28000000
	3955727	1535299	1794223	2582401	962683	1685809	1987681	1423553	1934879	3032321	1878841	2718193	2464117	44273	28000000
	1198403	2634131	2120579	3397967	3677291	3663311	3498743	2321243	2191373	7793	3923	353	83	3284807	28000000
	28000000	28000000	28000000	28000000	28000000	28000000	28000000	28000000	28000000	28000000	28000000	28000000	28000000	28000000	28000000

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 14. The internal block is a prime magic square of order 12 composed of **different sums prime magic squares** of order 3. It is the same as given in Example 20

Example 30. Block-Bordred Nested Prime Magic Square.Let’s consider a following prime magic square:

14	mgc														14000042
	1843687	427429	514519	394099	1028149	1795273	870403	897067	343963	1926703	1666237	254833	1733527	304153	14000042
	1801897	424819	1788037	787153	101749	1943827	954433	840943	1998133	160933	1343983	822517	833509	198109	14000042
	642163	1362337	1000003	637669	1852687	1000003	147319	319993	1000003	1680013	489529	1000003	1510477	1357843	14000042
	56809	1212853	211969	1575187	1045573	56179	1898257	1839073	1873	1159063	1166497	1177489	656023	1943197	14000042
	1786909	1200673	1122739	676597	606673	1738783	654553	961879	222067	1816063	1308943	89413	1601653	213097	14000042
	460063	475927	1000003	1524079	1047883	1000003	952123	1854187	1000003	145819	1292713	1000003	707293	1539943	14000042
	1458469	1323409	877267	799333	1345453	261223	1393333	183943	1777939	1038127	398353	1910593	691063	541537	14000042
	304687	1224859	433267	1341883	553933	1514659	931417	303679	1528237	1168093	682483	1968817	348709	1695319	14000042
	609619	1117027	1000003	882979	1377487	1000003	622519	1864417	1000003	135589	666229	1000003	1333777	1390387	14000042
	465679	658123	1566739	775147	1068589	485347	1446073	831913	471769	1696327	1651297	31189	1317523	1534327	14000042
	1520473	734143	1588183	677683	596839	1813387	589783	1084459	1815817	99733	374299	1928947	696763	479533	14000042
	968137	943543	1000003	1056463	992947	1000003	1007059	15277	1000003	1984729	1322467	1000003	677539	1031869	14000042
	385597	1322323	411823	1265863	1410223	186619	1403167	1900273	184189	915547	1303243	71059	1625707	1614409	14000042
	1695853	1572577	1485487	1605907	971857	204733	1129603	1102939	1656043	73303	333769	1745173	266479	156319	14000042
	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 14. The internal block is a prime magic square of order 12 composed of **equal sums prime magic squares** of order 3. It is the same as given in Example 21

Example 31. Block-Bordred Nested Prime Magic Square.Let’s consider a following prime magic square:

14	mgc														29349278
	4184437	1650157	299197	1229377	1250917	1799107	877333	1913941	1698061	1440211	4085677	4144633	2788033	1988197	29349278
	1776757	1298027	2293883	1550567	2039671	2032687	2101483	2364727	2483827	2013119	1847357	2542999	2588177	2415997	29349278
	1573477	1737523	1241699	1959593	2243333	2384653	2386861	2397049	1814161	1867913	2282149	2365469	2476121	2619277	29349278
	606313	2348441	1384727	2596129	852851	1924033	1460497	2738317	2859877	2165921	1093307	3250727	2481697	3586441	29349278
	772003	1798157	2261839	1075859	2046293	2641351	3033883	1482631	1824859	2944699	3768839	832457	1445657	3420751	29349278
	510241	2520577	2090219	2963333	2620883	2247851	2585417	1616623	1935617	1817801	1081793	2045567	1630843	3682513	29349278
	804283	2028263	2536307	2612131	3018311	2217217	1653251	2561729	1953311	1282451	1516687	1883393	1893473	3388471	29349278
	259411	2946611	2262437	2784137	2201827	1809887	1777609	2392919	2405093	2159881	1745897	1430027	1240199	3933343	29349278
	545521	2699561	3306049	1835411	2353991	2110553	2369231	1814237	2091487	1315871	2231627	1217017	1811489	3647233	29349278
	3629287	2019569	2082539	1518563	2158693	2179327	2506547	1688741	1413677	2859137	2098697	2322797	2308237	563467	29349278
	4142371	2357923	1466243	1993067	1962131	2221403	1458071	1685911	2422907	2634319	2493347	2097803	2363399	50383	29349278
	4174993	1692161	1917893	2402161	1767149	1724981	3026123	1618187	1419001	2427281	3514697	1483021	2163869	17761	29349278
	4165627	1709711	2312689	1865573	1891391	1662581	797551	2795453	2532707	1668131	1482127	3685247	2753363	27127	29349278
	2204557	2542597	3893557	2963377	2941837	2393647	3315421	2278813	2494693	2752543	107077	48121	1404721	8317	29349278
	29349278	29349278	29349278	29349278	29349278	29349278	29349278	29349278	29349278	29349278	29349278	29349278	29349278	29349278	29349278

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 14. The internal block is a prime magic square of order 12 composed of **different sums prime magic squares** of order 4. It is the same as given in Example 21

Example 32. Block-Bordered Nested Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

14	mgc														14000042
	1688677	456193	998419	734047	1590229	412663	880483	1926523	34039	280537	1736767	1495279	1426753	339433	14000042
	7927	1688179	307669	1692337	311827	1693303	309223	1690783	306703	1695283	310729	1689277	304723	1992079	14000042
	1959619	315517	1998397	1609	1684489	313333	1993273	6733	1686673	314239	1991293	8713	1685767	40387	14000042
	204319	733	1690993	309013	1999273	439	1693639	306367	1999567	457	1696543	303463	1999549	1795687	14000042
	1267723	1995583	2953	1997053	4423	1992937	3877	1996129	7069	1990033	1447	1998559	9973	732283	14000042
	838837	1294123	706633	1293373	705883	1299583	706267	1293739	700423	1306519	710293	1289713	693487	1161169	14000042
	626323	710257	1994479	5527	1289749	707467	1989019	10987	1292539	695917	1982083	17923	1304089	1373683	14000042
	938359	3643	1296613	703393	1996363	4993	1300633	699373	1995013	15823	1306849	693157	1984183	1061647	14000042
	945409	1991989	2287	1997719	8017	1987969	4093	1995913	12037	1981753	787	1999219	18253	1054597	14000042
	878659	1174759	836449	1163557	825247	1113877	893029	1106977	886129	1125127	897469	1102537	874879	1121347	14000042
	633379	831367	1977817	22189	1168639	906649	1974787	25219	1093357	905449	1963537	36469	1094557	1366627	14000042
	1699219	19483	1178173	821833	1980523	14629	1123807	876199	1985377	10729	1129957	870049	1989277	300787	14000042
	651019	1974403	7573	1992433	25603	1964857	8389	1991617	35149	1958707	9049	1990957	41299	1348987	14000042
	1660573	1543813	1001587	1265959	409777	1587343	1119523	73483	1965967	1719469	263239	504727	573253	311329	14000042
	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 14. The internal block is a prime magic square of order 12 composed of **equal sums prime magic squares** of order 4. It is the same as given in Example 23

Example 33. Equal Sum Blocks Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

14	mgc													14000042	
	751987	599479	1276903	1178953	1192879	463363	717139	895387	1404427	1484629	698077	747049	1382533	1207237	14000042
	830359	306049	1520509	328327	1552123	877873	1415137	1299379	715237	1429543	422869	1488337	644653	1169647	14000042
	1554559	1168477	1335409	481693	1518313	664597	831529	1234837	1407619	521743	1478263	592387	765169	445447	14000042
	468913	686437	980593	934693	1065313	1019413	1313569	1537279	613507	1280473	719533	1386499	462727	1531093	14000042
	1088827	1504033	930547	1516639	483367	1069459	495973	492853	516673	1225879	774127	1483333	1507153	911179	14000042
	1683373	1750153	753463	1066987	933019	1246543	249853	80317	1462213	971917	1028089	537793	1919689	316633	14000042
	1395817	584869	479497	1671679	447883	1122133	1693957	1355353	1284769	570463	1577137	511669	700627	604189	14000042
	881197	1865917	358447	672223	1407877	1482457	213097	214237	942013	1458463	330859	1302739	1751707	1118809	14000042
	1322227	310789	1449979	566947	1433059	550027	1689217	1258753	1587973	660277	1339729	412033	741253	677779	14000042
	1491643	1328749	477847	980557	1019449	1522159	671257	879283	826723	1348129	651877	1173283	1120723	508363	14000042
	415603	511867	1197649	1555999	444007	802357	1488139	1461283	621337	1972123	27883	1378669	538723	1584403	14000042
	969139	195787	874537	896509	1103497	1125469	1804219	1938163	963979	19483	1980523	1036027	61843	1030867	14000042
	353629	1786909	1641559	1327783	592129	517549	134089	248299	1057993	541543	1669147	697267	1785769	1646377	14000042
	792769	1400527	723103	821053	807127	1536643	1282867	1104619	595579	515377	1301929	1252957	617473	1248019	14000042
	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042

It is **equal sum block prime magic square** of order 14. It is composed of four equal sums **single-layer bordered** prime magic squares of order 7.

Example 34. Block-Bordred Nested Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

14	mgc													14000042	
	1217509	858373	842173	1234333	682777	1258597	906259	1405309	536233	407383	1482763	1289623	1569187	309523	14000042
	497773	931597	474337	1006087	1254637	1333357	1502233	935827	408223	1321513	1004287	368323	1897669	1064179	14000042
	1002787	1506607	1668229	311197	1020583	493399	997219	1197433	1357549	1623403	423259	953347	642457	802573	14000042
	1612393	392893	352357	1000003	1647649	1607113	387613	295663	1356577	329947	1000003	1670059	643429	1704343	14000042
	721843	1502269	979423	1688809	331777	497737	1278163	1097029	1775329	1046659	1576747	376603	224677	902977	14000042
	853969	666649	1525669	993919	745369	1068409	1146037	378277	102337	678493	995719	1631683	1591783	1621729	14000042
	1093747	1141633	1157833	765673	1317229	741409	782497	1690483	1463773	1592623	517243	710383	430819	594697	14000042
	854929	1416223	666889	279607	1044739	1484467	1253167	923743	1247479	1118809	1034599	409609	1086523	1179259	14000042
	1417597	1106593	353629	1180507	1106779	1252507	582409	819487	920833	1170277	1008229	509263	1391413	1180519	14000042
	1421227	531793	1492069	955147	552793	1468213	578779	690787	404449	872323	465679	1662007	1595557	1309219	14000042
	868849	1108147	60727	1000003	1939279	891859	1131157	295777	1279177	1789687	1000003	210319	720829	1704229	14000042
	1015753	1505983	1447213	1044859	507937	494023	984253	1470067	1786963	337999	1534327	1127683	213043	529939	14000042
	674827	747499	1646377	819499	893227	893413	1325179	1979413	608593	829729	991777	1490743	1079173	20593	14000042
	746839	583783	1333117	1720399	955267	515539	1145077	820747	752527	881197	965407	1590397	913483	1076263	14000042
	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042	14000042

*It is **block-wise prime magic square** of order 14. It is composed of four **equal sums single-layer bordered prime magic squares** of order 7. The center point of each blocks of order 7 is same in all the four blocks, i.e., 1000003. See below two examples for verification:*

3	mgc				3000009				3	mgc				3000009										
	1668229	311197	1020583	3000009						1492069	955147	552793	3000009											
	352357	1000003	1647649	3000009						60727	1000003	1939279	3000009											
	979423	1688809	331777	3000009						1447213	1044859	507937	3000009											
	3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009						3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009											
5	mgc						5000015			5	mgc						5000015							
	931597	474337	1006087	1254637	1333357	5000015				1106593	353629	1180507	1106779	1252507	5000015									
	1506607	1668229	311197	1020583	493399	5000015				531793	1492069	955147	552793	1468213	5000015									
	392893	352357	1000003	1647649	1607113	5000015				1108147	60727	1000003	1939279	891859	5000015									
	1502269	979423	1688809	331777	497737	5000015				1505983	1447213	1044859	507937	494023	5000015									
	666649	1525669	993919	745369	1068409	5000015				747499	1646377	819499	893227	893413	5000015									
	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015				5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015									
7	mgc								7000021			7	mgc								7000021			
	1217509	858373	842173	1234333	682777	1258597	906259	7000021			854929	1416223	666889	279607	1044739	1484467	1253167	7000021						
	497773	931597	474337	1006087	1254637	1333357	1502233	7000021			1417597	1106593	353629	1180507	1106779	1252507	582409	7000021						
	1002787	1506607	1668229	311197	1020583	493399	997219	7000021			1421227	531793	1492069	955147	552793	1468213	578779	7000021						
	1612393	392893	352357	1000003	1647649	1607113	387613	7000021			868849	1108147	60727	1000003	1939279	891859	1131157	7000021						
	721843	1502269	979423	1688809	331777	497737	1278163	7000021			1015753	1505983	1447213	1044859	507937	494023	984253	7000021						
	853969	666649	1525669	993919	745369	1068409	1146037	7000021			674827	747499	1646377	819499	893227	893413	1325179	7000021						
	1093747	1141633	1157833	765673	1317229	741409	782497	7000021			746839	583783	1333117	1720399	955267	515539	1145077	7000021						
	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021			7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021						

Example 35. Single-Layer Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

14	mgc														7000000
	799343	149867	64661	221603	23357	81233	145967	889937	901133	942749	774491	905453	976883	123323	7000000
	54269	109001	192617	318161	246473	173429	133877	460829	836117	948581	996323	975083	609509	945731	7000000
	352349	22643	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	977357	647651	7000000
	113489	70997	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	929003	886511	7000000
	266177	352511	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	647489	733823	7000000
	30539	120299	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	879701	969461	7000000
	2903	65921	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	934079	997097	7000000
	277757	989939	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	10061	722243	7000000
	982769	919823	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	80177	17231	7000000
	812627	963701	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	36299	187373	7000000
	782501	997793	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	2207	217499	7000000
	705821	996881	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	3119	294179	7000000
	942779	390491	807383	681839	753527	826571	866123	539171	163883	51419	3677	24917	890999	57221	7000000
	876677	850133	935339	778397	976643	918767	854033	110063	98867	57251	225509	94547	23117	200657	7000000
	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000	7000000

It is concentric single-layer bordered prime magic square of order 14. The internal concentric single-layer bordered prime magic square of order 12 is the same as given in Example 25.

4 Author’s Contribution to Recreation of Numbers and Magic Squares

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